

Articles on RESIST Community of Practice

Deliverable N. 2.1

21 January 2025

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Deliverable Name	Articles on the RESIST Community of Practice
Related Work Package	2
Deliverable lead	ERRIN
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Project Full Name	Regions for climate change resilience through Innovation, Science and Technology
Project Acronym	RESIST
Grant Agreement Number	101093968
Instrument	IA
Start date	01/01/2023
Duration	60 months
Type of Delivery (R, DEM, DEC, Other)¹	R
Dissemination Level (PU, CO, CI)²	PU
Date last update	20/01/2025
Website	resist-project.eu

¹ **R**=Document, report; **DEM**=Demonstrator, pilot, prototype; **DEC**=website, patent filings, videos, etc.; **OTHER**=other

² **PU**=Public, **CO**=Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services), **CI**=Classified

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Revision n° X	Date	Description	Author(s)
0.1	30/11/2023	First draft	Agnieszka Wieczorek Jetha (ERRIN)
0.2	14/12/2023	Comments and suggestions from co-authors	Gaia Marotta (ERRIN)
0.3	12/01/2024	Final edits	Agnieszka Wieczorek Jetha (ERRIN)
0.4	19/01/2024	First internal review	Silvia Cibien (ACCENT SUD)
0.5	22/01/2024	Second internal review	Catarina Azevedo (INOVA+)
0.6	26/01/2024	Third internal review	Vilija Balionyte-Merle (SINTEF)
0.7	30/01/2024	Fourth internal review	Gaia Marotta (ERRIN)
0.8	31/01/2024	Final version	Agnieszka Wieczorek Jetha (ERRIN)
0.9	22/11/2024	Update – first draft	Agnieszka Wieczorek Jetha (ERRIN)
0.10	10/12/2024	Update – final draft	Agnieszka Wieczorek Jetha (ERRIN)
0.11	17/12/2024	Internal review	Vilija Balionyte-Merle (SINTEF)
0.12	23/12/2024	Internal Review	Silvia Cibien (ACCENT SUD)
0.13	06/01/2025	Internal review	Catarina Azevedo (INOVA+)
0.14	20/01/2025	Final version	Agnieszka Wieczorek Jetha (ERRIN)

Please cite this deliverable as:

The articles of the RESIST Community of Practice, Deliverable 2.1 of the RESIST project.

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1 List of abbreviations

RESIST	Regions for climate change resilience through Innovation, Science and Technology
CoP	Community of Practice
CoI	Community of Interest
LSDT	Large-scale demonstrators and twins
LW	Local workshops
WP	Work Package

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2 Glossary

Community of Interest (CoI)	<p>A Community of Interest (CoI) within the project includes the members of the Community of Practice (CoP) alongside additional regions and their wide ecosystems of actors, fostering a broader community engaged in the activities promoting project outcomes and fostering closer dialogue with external stakeholders, including other projects. This extended network promotes collaboration, knowledge exchange, and relationship-building among stakeholders who share common interests and objectives related to the project's goals.</p>
Community of Practice (CoP)	<p>The CoP can be defined as the group composed of the stakeholders from the four Large Scale Demonstrators and the eight Twinning Regions and project partners. The activities carried out involve as well horizontal partners due to their role in supporting regions in the project.</p> <p>A Community of Practice stimulates cross-organisation collaboration, knowledge sharing and relationship building as 'groups of people who share a concern or a passion for something they do and learn how to do it better as they interact regularly' (Lave and Wenger, 1991 and 1996).</p>
Mutual learning	<p>Mutual learning refers to the collaborative engagement of members within the CoP and the CoI, taking into consideration the diverse needs, interests, motivations, and available time and resources of individuals and organisations. It involves a multifaceted approach to knowledge sharing and learning, fostering an environment that encourages continuous exchange of ideas, experiences, and expertise among the CoP members. The goal is to create a dynamic learning community where participants can benefit collectively from their shared insights and varied perspectives. This activity is foreseen in the frame of in-person CoP meetings and thematic webinars, where open exchanges are organised.</p>
Peer learning	<p>Peer learning involves collaborative efforts between two or more regions within a Community of Practice that are facing similar challenges or working on similar solutions. This approach facilitates the exchange of experiences, best practices, and lessons learned between peers who share common goals or issues. This activity is foreseen to start in 2025 in the form of parallel sessions on Transferable Solutions for "receiving" and "providing" regions. A wider peer learning will be also enabled in</p>

	open Col webinars, where participation of other regions and projects is foreseen.
Quadruple helix	A collaborative model involving four key stakeholders—government, industry, academia, and civil society—working together in an integrated and synergistic manner to address complex challenges, foster innovation, and promote sustainable development. This approach emphasises the active involvement and cooperation of representatives of these four sectors to create a more dynamic and inclusive innovation ecosystem.
Quintuple helix	Quintuple Helix is an innovation model that builds upon the Quadruple Helix by incorporating the fifth helix, representing the "natural environments of society." In addition to government, industry, academia, civil society, and media, this framework recognises the crucial role of environmental considerations in shaping innovation and development. The Quintuple Helix underscores the need to integrate sustainability, ecological awareness, and environmental responsibility into collaborative efforts, ensuring a holistic approach to innovation that considers the impact on the natural world within the broader socio-economic context.

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3 Introduction

This document presents an updated comprehensive framework for the Community of Practice (CoP), aiming to provide information and strategies for the RESIST partners to effectively establish, manage, and improve the CoP, ensuring that this community remains impactful, relevant, and sustainable.

The framework is structured around five key sections that cover the essential components and processes for establishing and managing a successful CoP. These sections include:

1. Objectives and rules
2. Implementing the Community of Practice
3. Planned activities of the Community of Practice
4. Community of Interest (CoI) and its alignment with the CoP
5. Next steps

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4 CoP objectives and rules

Task 2.1, *Networking and mutual learning layer*, led by ERRIN, focuses on establishing and enhancing the RESIST Community of Practice through a comprehensive networking and mutual learning layer. The RESIST CoP consists of 12 regions vulnerable to climate risks, which form the backbone of the RESIST consortium. These regions and all their relevant stakeholders have an aim of exchanging on the existing challenges, needs and gaps, as well as building on the developing solutions, scaling them up and creating resilience against the impacts of climate change, as set in the objectives of the **Mission**.

Figure 1 The objectives of the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change

During the first year of the project (M1-M12), the activities focused on the identification of needs in order to plan a mutual learning scheme tailored to the specific requirements of both the Large Scale Demonstrators and Twinning Regions. ERRIN, in collaboration with WP3 -*Large Scale collaborative Demonstrators (LSD) and Twinning activities for climate resilient innovation* - discussed with the twelve regions their innovations, challenges, and expectations to co-define the CoP activities. This input has been fundamental to the design of the work plan and to creating collaborations among the twelve regions for knowledge-sharing and replication of climate change adaptation (CCA) innovations from M12.

During the project's second year, ERRIN continued close dialogue with all the regions and provided information sessions and in-person workshops for the RESIST partners. The dialogue with the Mission Adaptation Secretariat of the European Commission has been reinforced, focusing on an alignment in the CoP's activities with the MIP4Adapt initiatives (Futurium).

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As of the third year, the RESIST CoP will expand into a Community of Interest to be launched in March 2025, and will invite additional front-runners and less experienced regions interested in participating in the mutual learning scheme. Open webinars and workshops will be organised, integrating key methods and tools developed in the projects, showcasing success stories and sharing knowledge with other relevant projects and other external stakeholders. These activities are set to reflect the current developments of the project and are continuously cross-referenced with other Work Packages and project partners (in particular, WP1, WP3 and WP5). Within the Work Packages there are relevant tasks which aim to foster collaboration with and among the project partner regions, and with which the Community of Practice stays in collaboration:

Task 1.1	Climate adaptation framework for demonstration activities.
Task 1.4	Impact monitoring & ethics/gender analysis framework.
Task 2.3	Upscaling towards other entrepreneurial ecosystems.
Task 4.1	Social impacts through transformative social innovation.
Task 5.4	Advisory Board and External Relations.

Table 1 Project Tasks collaborating with the regions and related to the Community of Practice

4.1 Identifying the general purpose of the CoP

In order to attract and engage members, a CoP must offer a compelling value proposition demonstrating the benefits and opportunities of participating in the community. This value proposition should be based on the CoP's purpose and objectives and should outline the specific ways in which the CoP will support its members in achieving their goals and addressing their challenges.

The first step in establishing the RESIST CoP was to identify a set of specific needs or opportunities that the CoP could address. This work was based on needs assessment activities carried out within the RESIST project³, as well as exchanges with the project partners and input provided by the 12 regions. By focusing on a clear set of needs or challenges, project partners could ensure that the CoP is purpose-driven and aligned with the strategic priorities of the project.

Once a set of needs and challenges have been identified, the next step is to define the CoP's purpose and objectives. This involves articulating the community's overarching mission, as well as the specific outcomes and impacts it seeks to achieve. In defining these objectives, ERRIN engaged with the twelve regions and the project horizontal partners who have conducted the need assessment activities and defined four main objectives:

- Address various climate risk challenges tackled by the partner regions

³ D1.1 – Needs Assessment For Leading Regions

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- Provide a space for networking, collaboration and exchanges for the partner regions
- Ensure communication and information flow between regions
- Develop a mutual learning scheme

4.2 Engaging with the target group

In order to create a long-lasting and effective collaboration, the first efforts were focused on getting to know the regions by participating in LSDTs meetings under WP3. This process included a bottom-up conversation and survey on the key topics and priorities, which now serve as a backbone for the CoP plan. As the project develops, keeping this conversation going is a priority for a useful and efficient exchange and mutual learning process. Therefore, the topics of interest are planned to be verified at every in-person meeting during the RESIST consortium meeting and updated, if necessary.

By providing opportunities for active participation, a sense of ownership and commitment will continue to be fostered among the CoP members, ensuring that they remain invested in the community. This will involve showcasing member successes or good practices in adapting to climate change from different perspectives, within the CoP but also on a wider scale, during the open Col webinars. The CoP will offer a range of learning and development opportunities, such as workshops or webinars, tailored to their members' needs and interests. This can involve regular opportunities for networking, collaboration, and social interaction, as well as providing a supportive environment for open dialogue, knowledge sharing, and learning.

4.3 Establishing the structure for exchanges

Effective structure and ownership are critical to the success and sustainability of the Community of Practice. A well-defined structure, coupled with leadership, ensures that CoP can effectively coordinate its activities, make strategic decisions, and foster a sense of commitment among their members. This section provides an overview of the key principles and considerations for establishing robust structure and leadership within the CoP.

Structural levels for the RESIST CoP exchanges consist of various types of collaborations and meetings (in-person and online), ensuring a regular and comprehensive dialogue between the regions, as well as with other relevant horizontal project partners. This includes:

- In-person meetings:
 - Community of Practice meetings at the RESIST consortium meetings, which are set to discuss the most relevant project developments and crucial thematic issues, such as communication and stakeholder engagement, or digital technologies and nature-

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based solutions. It also comprises regions' involvement in other relevant project tasks.

- Online meetings to be organised on different levels within the consortium:
 - Thematic workshops organised in collaboration with WP2 Task 2.3. These webinars will be organised twice a year and focus on topics selected by the regional partners during the Consortium Meeting in Extremadura on 27/11/2024 (however the thematic preferences and needs of the regional partners will be also collected on other occasions in future).
 - Exchange on Transferable Solutions between the “providing regions”, which will form the main mutual learning activity.
 - Exchange on Transferable Solutions between the “receiving regions”, which will form the main mutual learning activity.
 - Looser exchange with all regions on solutions currently developed, which are not selected for the solution transfers. The topics were selected by the regional partners during the Consortium Meeting in Extremadura on 27/11/2024 and will be updated during the project's duration in accordance with regions' needs.
 - Other exchanges with horizontal project partners and Advisory Board. They will be involved in the thematic group's activities to contribute to the activities, providing expertise and advice during webinars, workshops and exchanges. The topics will be reviewed regularly and adjusted based on regional needs.

The calendar of activities and more details can be found in the section 5.6.

4.4 Community levels in RESIST

The RESIST Community is defined by three levels of engagement as specified below:

Figure 2 Community levels in RESIST

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- 1. REGIONAL PROJECT PARTNERS:** The core of the project is made of the 57 partners⁴ from the EU, Norway and Ukraine constituting the RESIST Consortium; RESIST brings forward an open, incremental approach to establish and develop climate-resilient adaptation solutions for, with and in four vulnerable regional ecosystems: Southwest Finland (FI), Central Denmark (DK), Catalonia (ES) and Centro Portugal (PT, this one a less developed region), directly addressing approximately 12 million people. For each of these regions, local stakeholders representing the quintuple-helix approach are involved in the partnership together with Regional Authorities, incl. leading research partners such as Turku's University and University of Applied Sciences, Aarhus University, VIA, U. Politecnica de Catalunya and Polytechnic Portalegre, businesses as Hyds, NIRAS, ForestWise cluster and Union of Agricultural Producers and Forest Owners of Finland (associate) and municipalities and associations representing civil sector. Each of these front-runner demonstrator regions is paired with two less experienced Twinning Regions with similar vulnerabilities, of which half are less developed regions. These are Normandy (FR), East Macedonia and Thrace (GR), Blekinge (SE), Zemgale (LV), Puglia (IT), Baixo-Alentejo (PT), Vesteralen (NO) and Extremadura (ES).
- 2. COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE:** The RESIST Community of Practice consists of 12 regions (four Large Scale demonstrators and eight Twinning Regions) involved in the project and their local ecosystem – representatives of pilots and leading organisations who face different challenges and present different approaches to tackling them. Insights into regions' innovations for climate change adaptation, their challenges, and their expectations will be explored and discussed in order to develop a mutual learning scheme tailored to the different needs of both the demonstrator and Twinning Regions. Other project partners and the project Advisory Board will be invited to give expertise and advice on topics related to their specialisations. The scheme will serve to facilitate knowledge-sharing and peer learning, firstly in the CoP and then into a broader Community of Interest.
- 3. COMMUNITY OF INTEREST:** The third level of engagement concerns the Community of Interest, which aims to bring together the representatives of additional regions and other linked stakeholders and initiatives. Open events will be organised in collaboration with other EU-funded projects and will host relevant experts and invite relevant projects and other stakeholders. The activities will aim to showcase RESIST success stories in front of a wide audience and create long-lasting collaborations. It will also become an additional opportunity for mutual learning and experience sharing.

⁴ As of 24 January 2024.

4.5 Defining roles and responsibilities

Effective leadership within the CoP requires strong collaboration and communication among stakeholders. Regional coordinators should work to create an environment that encourages open dialogue, information sharing, and joint problem-solving, fostering a sense of trust and mutual support among CoP members.

The regions have already defined the person responsible for this role through an internal competence matrix developed in WP 3, *Large Scale Collaborative Demonstrators (LSD)*, and *Twinning activities for climate-resilient innovation*.

Throughout the duration of the project, it became clear that not only partners directly involved in the project's tasks are valued members of the Community of Practice, but also their whole ecosystems of actors. The collaboration of quadruple helix within regional ecosystems is crucial for the best possible outputs, and therefore all CoP activities are designed to involve, directly or indirectly, relevant stakeholders who's role is to transfer concrete examples and experiences e.g. via the online activities.

The communications carried out happens on the project level – between project partners. However, it is always underlined, that the invitations are extended to all relevant ecosystem actors who are encouraged to contribute to CoP's activities. The partner regions have a role to keep in close contact with the relevant actors and run dialogue on the ground, of which results are shared in the various CoP discussions.

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5 Implementing the Community of Practice

5.1 Topics and goals definition

The goal of the RESIST CoP is to provide a unique opportunity for networking and exchange of experiences, good practices, and project developments and learnings. The CoP will enable a space for a free exchange within a set-up structure suited to the particular challenges and issues faced by the regions. The Community will focus on crosscutting issues tackled by the partner regions and specific topics (methodological, climate risks and others). The topics are regularly assessed and adjusted to the main interests of the CoP members. Below the first interactions of such consultation are briefly described.

On the other hand, the first webinars and meetings already took place in 2024 and their summaries can be found in the sections below.

5.1.1 Survey to shape CoP priorities

In November 2023, a short survey was conducted collaboratively with Task 2.3, *Upscaling towards other entrepreneurial ecosystems*. The primary objective was to gather valuable input from the RESIST 12 regions, focusing on their preferences and expectations regarding key interests and challenges.

The ultimate goal was to shape the agenda of the Community of Practice and upcoming webinars dedicated to entrepreneurial ecosystems.

In the questionnaire, partners were asked to rank the challenges and topics from the most to the least relevant for the regions.

The suggested topics were the result of internal consultations with the regions within WP3, *Large-scale collaborative demonstrators (LSD) and Twinning activities for climate-resilient innovation*.

The list included the following topics and challenges:

- Lack of political support
- Lack of stakeholder/community engagement
- Limited knowledge of climate risks
- Absence of policies, regulations, norms or guidelines
- Challenges related to data collection
- Absence of clear financing models
- Lack of well-designed adaptation plans and strategies on the local and regional level.

Additionally, the survey inquired about regional participation in EU Mission-related events and activities. The responses to the survey have been collected and in the topics have been addressed at the first CoP workshop during the project Consortium meeting in Aalesund.

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Input shared through this initial survey helped also to shape further the CoP activities in 2024.

5.1.2 CoP kick-off: workshop in Aalesund

The official kick-off of the Community of Practice took place during the RESIST Consortium meeting in Aalesund from December 5th to 7th. The first CoP workshop was organised to discuss the challenges identified through the Survey, as mentioned above.

Four dedicated sessions, moderated by Clara Pinho (INOVA +), Gaia Marotta, Julie Delcroix, and Agnieszka Wiczorek Jetha (all from ERRIN), focused on four key challenges:

- the lack of political support,
- community/stakeholder engagement,
- limited knowledge of climate risks/data collection,
- and the absence of climate change policies, regulations, and adaptation strategies at the local and regional levels.

The workshop included an engaging introduction and a structured breakout session. The icebreaker activities were designed not only to gauge the participants' perceptions of the challenges but also to encourage active participation and networking. Participants were prompted to stand up based on their experiences, ranging from having best practices or solutions to challenges to those still searching for viable solutions.

The first goal of the workshop was to define the challenges associated with climate change adaptation within their regions. This involved discussing each challenge in relation to the different regional contexts and from the point of view of different stakeholders, including experts from the horizontal tasks. Following this, the workshop aimed to relate these challenges to specific local cases and experiences, enriching the discussions with real-world context and practical insights.

A crucial aspect of the workshop's goals was the integration of challenges with the needs assessment and existing know-how. Participants engaged in discussions to determine what tools and strategies were currently being developed to address the identified challenges. This step aimed to leverage the collective knowledge and experiences of the participants, fostering an environment of shared learning and collaboration.

Furthermore, the workshop facilitated discussions on the relevance of the selected challenges or topics for continued exploration within the CoP. Participants actively considered whether these challenges warranted ongoing attention and, if so, discussed what types of experts would be essential to involve in future discussions. This forward-thinking approach aimed to ensure that the CoP's agenda remained tailor-made and relevant for regional stakeholders. The facilitators, including Clara Pinho, Gaia Marotta, Julie Delcroix, and Agnieszka Wiczorek Jetha, guided these sessions, ensuring that the workshops were dynamic, participatory, and conducive to idea generation.

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To gather diverse perspectives and insights, all participants were encouraged to write down their inputs on sticky notes. Some participants volunteered to read aloud their contributions, fostering a collaborative atmosphere where various voices were heard. For each question posed, a short discussion ensued, allowing for exchanging ideas, opinions, and potential solutions. The participatory nature of the workshop, coupled with the structured approach to goal achievement, contributed to a successful and productive event that laid the groundwork for continued collaboration within the RESIST Community of Practice.

Figure 3 First CoP Workshop

Post-breakout sessions, the outputs were presented by Jesse de Pagter (ZSI), Linda Hoelscher, Daria Gettueva (both from ADELPHI), and Danny Vandenbroucke (KU LEUVEN). These presentations encapsulated the wealth of insights, potential solutions, and collaborative efforts that emerged during the workshop.

As a result, three main workstreams emerged:

- stakeholder engagement in climate adaptation activities,
- a coordinated approach to adaptation strategies and regulations with political support for implementation,
- and advancing knowledge on climate risks alongside the coordination of data collection efforts.

This form of exchange was very appreciated by the partner regions and it will be considered in the future activities.

5.1.3 Prioritisation of themes in Extremadura

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In November 2024, during the Consortium Meeting in Plasencia, Extremadura, the following topics were selected for the CoP activities (the list is not exclusive but includes the most crosscutting topics for all regions):

- Stakeholder engagement in climate adaptation activities
- Knowledge of climate risks and coordination of data collection
- Communication and awareness raising
- Citizen awareness activities (communication, storytelling, narratives, activities)
- How to communicate about climate change
- Use of digital solutions (XR, VR, graphic visualisations)
- NbS adaptation by stakeholders
- Nature-based solutions (NbS)
- How CAP is fostering NbS in different countries

As of 2025, the key topics to be tackled will be reassessed through a yearly survey and adapted according to the review carried out with all the regions. As the project advances, the needs will change, and so relevant improvements will be introduced.

5.2 CoP in-person meetings and webinars carried out to date

The Community of Practice (CoP) targets the internal stakeholders of RESIST. As of the current date, five CoP meetings have been convened, consisting of three in-person sessions held within the context of consortium meetings and two conducted online.

In-person CoP session: CoP kick-off

The initial meeting, described in the previous paragraph, focused on identifying the requisites for a mutual learning scheme tailored to the specific needs of both the Large-Scale Demonstrators and Twinning Regions.

Online CoP session: info session on MIP4Adapt Platform

48 people attended the second CoP meeting on 15 March 2024, which was conducted as an online informational session concerning the MIP4Adapt platform, encompassing the services available for the regions and the potential for collaborations. The presentation focused on the support that is provided within the Community of Practice as well as the Technical Assistance, which focuses on stakeholder and citizen engagement, adaptation planning, and access to relevant funding and financing.

Online CoP session: Stakeholders' engagement

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This meeting took place online on 16 May 2024, and 40 people joined. Experts from horizontal partners and external stakeholders have been invited to contribute to the meeting, presenting their strategies and best practices. The session started with an overview by Stefan Philipp, from ZSI, of the different stakeholders' engagement strategies, how they target different stakeholders' groups and what expected outcomes are in mind. This was followed by an interactive moment among regions across LSDTs, enabling LSD and Twinning Regions to exchange and characterise their respective challenges and lessons learnt from their own practices. In particular, four cases have been presented:

- Communication and dissemination activities in Vesterålen - The Gaia Museum
- Involvement of decision-makers in Central Denmark - The Danish Climate Game
- Collaboration with academia in decision-making in Catalonia - Academia's role in the quadruple-Helix collaboration
- Involvement of the private sector in Southwest Finland - Involvement of farmers and industry sector

In-person CoP session: Stakeholders engagement

The second CoP meeting on stakeholders' engagement took place in person in the context of the project Consortium Meeting in Vesterålen in June 2024. As a continuation of the previous session, four parallel sessions were organised on the following topics:

- Table 1: Engagement of Academia – Focus on Normandy
- Table 2: Engagement of public and private decision-makers – Focus on Blekinge
- Table 3: Citizens' engagement – Focus on Central Denmark
- Table 4: Engagement of Landowners and local communities – Focus on Centro Portugal

In-person CoP session: Shaping the agenda of further exchanges

The third CoP meeting on stakeholders' engagement took place in person in the context of the project Consortium Meeting in Extremadura in November 2024 and was attended by around 80 participants. Regions and other horizontal partners were asked to provide their input on the way ahead concerning future CoP activities. The conclusions can be found in the Annex.

Both the Large-Scale Demonstrators and Twinning regions have taken part in the CoP meetings and have been asked to extend the invitation to their local stakeholders for webinars. The project partners associated with the twelve regions have consistently joined at the CoP meetings, presenting their examples and engaging in discussions on challenges and existing solutions.

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5.3 Collaboration and learning formats foreseen

5.3.1 Mutual learning activities

Events and activities play a vital role in fostering collaboration, knowledge sharing, and learning within the CoP, as indicated in the introduction. By organising a diverse range of events and exchanges tailored to the needs and interests of its members, opportunities for networking and engagement with the CoP's objectives will be fostered. To ensure that its events and activities are impactful and aligned with the CoP's goals, the following steps will be implemented:

- **Planning and organising community events:**

Coordinate various events and activities supporting the CoP's goals, such as workshops, webinars, and information sessions for its members. Ensure that these events are relevant and engaging and provide an opportunity for exchange.

- **Identifying relevant external events and opportunities for collaboration:**

Monitor and share information on external events, funding opportunities, and collaboration possibilities that align with the CoP's interests. Encourage members to participate in these events and leverage them to strengthen the CoP's network and impact. A link to the Mission Adaptation activities under MIP4Adapt has been made in this regard.

- **Facilitate exchanges in smaller groups to enable efficient mutual learning:**

This will be organised as of 2025 and divided by topic/type of exchange. As mentioned above, a calendar of activities has been created to organise mutual learning with regards to the developed Transfer Plans, other climate solutions and other project developments.

To ensure its events and activities are effective and aligned with the CoP's objectives, ERRIN will regularly assess their impact and gather participant feedback. This can be achieved through a variety of methods, such as post-event calls for inputs or dialogue with attendees. By collecting and analysing this feedback, areas for improvement will be identified to adjust its programming accordingly and better meet the needs and expectations. ERRIN will also strengthen the interactivity of each activity and foster lively exchanges.

5.3.2 Encouraging peer learning

One of the most effective ways to build capacity within the RESIST CoP is to encourage peer learning and collaboration between regions facing similar challenges or developing similar solutions. Peer-to-peer activities facilitate the exchange of experiences, best practices, and lessons learned between peers who share common goals or issues. By fostering cross-community learning, the transfer of

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knowledge, skills, and best practices across CoP will be facilitated while also promoting greater cohesion and collaboration within the regional innovation ecosystem. The peer learning scheme will be expanded with the involvement of CoI members.

The peer learning will be fostered during the exchanges between “receiving” and “providing” regions with regards to the transfer of CCA solutions.

5.3.3 Exchange with experts and external stakeholders

In addition to providing capacity-building opportunities at the community level, RESIST will support individual capacity-building for its CoP members. This can involve guidance and support for members to pursue their own learning and development goals, such as attending conferences, workshops, or training courses outside of the CoP's activities. By supporting individual capacity building, the RESIST project can help to ensure that its CoP members remain engaged, motivated, and equipped to contribute effectively to the community's work.

As part of its strategic management guidelines, RESIST has set a goal to actively participate in the EU Mission on Adaptation activities and ensure that partners are active on the Mission Implementation Platform, which is running parallel to RESIST. In the framework of the CoP, ERRIN will act as a liaison, set up a dialogue with the Mission Secretariat, and pass on useful information and interesting opportunities coming from the EU Mission directly, aiming to scale up the mutual learning opportunities.

In reference to the Community of Interest (CoI), which targets the external stakeholders of RESIST, the project strategy aims to engage and involve existing communities of regions and local stakeholders within other EU Adaptation Mission projects rather than launch a new call for interest. This approach aligns with Task 5.4 Advisory Board and External Relations, reflecting a commitment to establishing robust collaboration with EU Mission projects for the sharing of project insights, examples, measures, and solutions.

An initial list of projects to engage, lasting beyond 2025, with divided by topical focus or type of potential collaboration can be found in the table below (*Table 1 Project Collaboration Overview*), a more comprehensive overview of the mapped projects can be found in *Annex 1 Project Collaboration Overview*. Moreover, in the context of task 5.4, this initial analysis will be completed and periodically updated.

The CoI activities will align with the Adaptation Mission Platform and depend on the EU Mission calendar of activities.

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Table 2 Project Collaboration Overview

Best practices sharing with regions involved	
ClimEmpower	User-driven climate applications empowering regional resilience
FARCLIMATE	Moving ForwARd to achieving CLIMATE-resilient and sustainable European regional economic systems
P2R	Co-developing pathways towards Climate resilient regions in Europe
Regions4Climate (R4C)	Regions4Climate (R4C)
Citizens engagement and societal resilience	
URBREATH	Systemic Integration of Transformative Technical and Nature-based Solutions to Improve Climate Neutrality of European Cities and Regions and tackle Climate Change: the URBreath Approach
Coastal regions and water management	
OCEANIDS	User-driven applications and tools for Climate-Informed Maritime Spatial Planning and integrated seascape management, towards a resilient & inclusive Blue Economy
SpongeBoost	Upscaling the natural sponge functions of freshwater ecosystems to deliver multi-benefit green deal solutions
SpongeScapes	Evidence and Solutions for improving SPONGE Functioning at LandSCAPE Scale in European Catchments for increased Resilience of Communities against Hydrometeorological Extreme Events
Digital solutions	
Regions4Climate (R4C)	Building resilient communities
CARDIMED	Climate Adaptation and Resilience Demonstrated In the MEDiterranean region

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Innovative financing mechanisms for climate adaptation

CLIMATEFIT Resilient CLIMATE Financing and Investment Taskforces

Innovative insurance solutions for climate change adaptation

PIISA Piloting Innovative Insurance Solutions for Adaptation

SOTERIA SOLutions TEsting for Regions through Insurance for climate Adaptation

Mountain regions

MountResilience Accelerating transformative climate adaptation for higher resilience in European mountain regions

NBS

ARCADIA TrAnsformative climate ResilienCe by nAture-baseD solutions in the contInentAl bio-geographical region

DesirMED Demonstration and mainstrEaming of nature-based Solutions for climate Resilient transformation in the MEDiterranean

LAND4CLIMATE Utilization Of Private Land For Mainstreaming Nature-Based Solution In The Systemic Transformation Towards A Climate-Resilient Europe

NATALIE Accelerating and mainstreaming transformative NATure-bAsed solutions to enhance resiLIence to climate change for diverse bio-geographical European regions

NBRACER Nature Based Solutions for Atlantic Regional Climate Resilience

CARDIMED Climate Adaptation and Resilience Demonstrated In the MEDiterranean region

Risk analysis and assessment

MIRACA Multi-hazard Infrastructure Risk Assessment for Climate Adaptation

CLIMAAX CLIMAtE risk and vulnerability Assessment framework and toolbox

Urban regeneration

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GreenInCities

Green In Cities

Use of data and data management
VALORADA

Validated Local Risk Actionable Data for Adaptation

5.4 CoP meetings calendar

To facilitate the collaboration within the CoP, a variety of opportunities for members to share their experiences, insights, and best practices with one another will be created. This will involve organising regular knowledge-sharing events, such as workshops and webinars. To promote diversity within the CoP, participation of regional stakeholders from different sectors and backgrounds will be encouraged, as well as those with varying levels of experience and expertise.

A calendar of CoP activities throughout the project can be found below. The exchanges will be organised on different collaboration levels: between LSDTs, solution providers and receivers, horizontal partners and Advisory Board.

		RESIST Community of Practice (CoP) and Community of Interest (CoI) activities for 2025											
ACRONYM	TYPE OF MEETING	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
COI meetings	Open webinars with external stakeholders			Webinar on digital technologies and Col kick-off							RESIST session or stand during EWRC	COI open workshop showcasing project results	
COP meetings	In-person sessions during the consortium meetings										COP mutual-learning workshop on thematic synergies		
COP TW	CoP Thematic online workshops	Online webinar on NBS and stakeholder engagement								Online workshop on communicating about climate adaptation			
COP LE	CoP looser exchange on solutions not selected for transfers (online or in person)				Online workshop on the use of digital technologies						Online workshop on coastal climate risks solutions		
COP E-P	CoP online exchange on solutions among "providing regions"					First exchange: sharing experiences so far							
COP E-R	CoP online exchange on solutions among "receiving regions"					First exchange: sharing experiences so far							
COP OE	Other online thematic exchanges with various Work Packages e.g. on digital twins, transfer plans, etc.		Online exchange with horizontal partners on transfer plans							Online exchange with horizontal partners on digital graphical twins			

Figure 4 Calendar of CoP and CoI activities in 2025

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RESIST Community of Practice (CoP) and Community of Interest (CoI) activities for 2026													
ACRONYM	TYPE OF MEETING	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
COI meetings	Open webinars with external stakeholders		COI thematic workshop showcasing project results								COI thematic workshop showcasing project results		
COP meetings	In-person sessions during the consortium meetings						COP capacity-building workshop						
COP TW	CoP Thematic online workshops			Online webinar on the sustainability of NBS								Online workshop on awareness raising and involvement of decisionmakers	
COP LE	CoP looser exchange on solutions not selected for transfers (online or in person)				Online workshop on gamification - knowledge sharing						Online workshop on good practices with stakeholder engagement		
COP E-P	CoP online exchange on solutions among "providing regions"									Second exchange: making transfers successful			
COP E-R	CoP online exchange on solutions among "receiving regions"									Second exchange: making transfers successful			
COP OE	Other online thematic exchanges with various Work Packages e.g. on digital twins, transfer plans, etc.					Online exchange with horizontal partners on transfer plans							

Figure 5 Calendar of CoP and CoI activities in 2026

RESIST Community of Practice (CoP) and Community of Interest (CoI) activities for 2027													
ACRONYM	TYPE OF MEETING	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
COI meetings	Open webinars with external stakeholders		Webinar on long-term impact of CCA solutions								RESIST session or stand during EWRC		COI showcasing project outcomes
COP meetings	In-person sessions during the consortium meetings												CoP final workshop
COP TW	CoP Thematic online workshops				Online webinar topic TBC					Online workshop topic TBC			
COP LE	CoP looser exchange on solutions not selected for transfers (online or in person)				Online exchange topic TBC								
COP E-P	CoP online exchange on solutions among "providing regions"					Online exchange topic TBC							
COP E-R	CoP online exchange on solutions among "receiving regions"					Online exchange topic TBC							
COP OE	Other online thematic exchanges with various Work Packages e.g. on digital twins, transfer plans, etc.			Online exchange topic TBC							Online exchange topic TBC		

Figure 6 Calendar of CoP and CoI activities in 2027

The different CoP and CoI activities have been spread across the duration of the project to reflect the ongoing developments and respond to the needs of relevant project partners and regions. The aim of the different levels of activities is linked to different expectations and exchange formats.

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5.4.1 CoP bi-yearly in person workshops

The partner regions forming the Community of Practice will meet in person at the RESIST Consortium meetings, whenever possible. These meetings will be run in the form of interactive workshops, aiming at capitalising on the progress made by the regions in the project, mutual learning activities and assessment of the topics to be tackled in the frame of the CoP in the following months.

The topics of the in person workshops will be as follows:

- On thematic synergies between the partner regions working on similar CCA solutions (October 2025)
- On capacity building and sustainability of project outputs (in June 2026)
- On long-term impact (in February/March 2027 TBC)
- The last exchange will be organised during the final meeting in 2027.

5.4.2 Thematic webinars and internal workshops

Informal and interactive online workshops will be organised twice a year in collaboration with SERN (WP2 task 2.3) where representatives from LSDTs meet online to share insights, best practices and know-how from experts from different fields on topics relevant to the design and implementation of the project methodology.

The format will last a maximum of two hours and will kick-off with the presentation, by LSDT partners, of the main highlights' activities related to the selected topic. The main goal is to present a specific aspect of the methodology and discuss its replication in other contexts. To ensure that, the regional representatives are also asked to showcase their local experience related to the meeting topic to foster mutual learning between CoP members.

They will provide an opportunity to hear from external experts, the RESIST Advisory Board and relevant partners about opportunities and solutions related to climate change adaptation.

The webinars are scheduled twice a year, in Q1 and Q3. The topics were collected in November 2024 and will be re-assessed after a year.

The rest of exchanges will happen mostly online, unless indicated otherwise in the calendar, and will be divided into:

- “Looser exchange”: webinars showcasing various solutions developed in the partner regions outside of the Transfer Plans in a form of mutual learning sessions for regions
- Peer-learning for regions “providing” and “receiving” solutions under the Transfer Plans
- Other exchanges for horizontal partners in order to align activities which involve regions.

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6 Community of Interest

As part of Task 2.1, *Networking and mutual learning layer*, ERRIN is also responsible for setting up a Community of Interest (CoI) which will involve wider community. The aim will be to further foster project's outreach, develop relationship with external stakeholders and projects, and engage additional front-runners and less experienced regions interested in sharing their challenges and experiences.

The Community of Interest will be organised in a form of open public events showcasing RESIST results and fostering the relationships with other projects and external stakeholders. A series of open events will be carried out, integrating key methods/tools developed in collaboration with partners to share knowledge and facilitate mutual learning.

The kick off of the Community of Interest is planned for 14 March 2025, during an open RESIST webinar on digital technologies. The event will be promoted on the MIP4Adapt platform and widely spread, to ensure diverse participation of European regions and other European projects. The webinar will focus on the novel combination of digital technologies that have been worked on in RESIST project: a technical repository prepared by KU Leuven (Belgium), a Graphical digital twin prepared by Augmentcity (Norway) and Shepherd proposed by SINTEF (Norway). These core elements can be reinforced by the emergency preparedness system developed by UPC (Catalonia) and XR/VR simulations (Blekinge) and more. A contribution of Regions4Climate project is also foreseen to strengthen the collaboration.

A calendar of CoI activities can be found in the section below.

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7 List of activities planned

The list below includes all events (in-person and online) planned for the duration of the project, both for the Community of Practice and Community of Interest. The topics have been reassessed in late 2024. After 2025, the Community of Practice will discuss the importance of these topics and adjust its programme for 2026 and going forward.

Activities planned for 2025:

Q1	CoP	Thematic webinar on NbS and stakeholder engagement (15 January)
	CoP	Online exchange with horizontal partners on transfer plans (February)
	CoI	Webinar on digital technologies and Community of Interest kick-off (14 March)
Q2	CoP	Online workshop on the use of digital technologies as a good practice (April)
	CoP	First exchange on Transfer Plans among the “providing regions”: sharing experiences so far (May)
	CoP	First exchange on Transfer Plans among the “receiving regions”: sharing experiences so far (May)
Q3	CoP	Thematic webinar on communicating about climate adaptation (September)
	CoP	Online exchange with horizontal partners on digital graphical twins (September)
	CoP	Online workshop on coastal climate risks solutions as a good practice (Autumn)
Q4	CoI	RESIST session or stand during the European Week of Regions and Cities (October)
	CoP	In-person mutual learning workshop on thematic synergies (October)
	CoI	Open workshop showcasing project results (November)

Activities planned for 2026:

Q1	CoI	Community of Interest - thematic workshop showcasing project results (February)
	CoP	Online webinar on the sustainability of NBS (March)
Q2	CoP	Online workshop on gamification - knowledge sharing (April)
	CoP	Online exchange with horizontal partners on transfer plans (May)

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	CoP	Capacity-building workshop (June)
Q3	CoP	Second exchange on Transfer Plans among the “receiving regions”: making transfers successful (September)
	CoP	Second exchange on Transfer Plans among the “providing regions”: making transfers successful (September)
Q4	Col	Thematic workshop showcasing project results (October)
	CoP	Online workshop on good practices with stakeholder engagement (October)
	CoP	Online workshop on awareness raising and involvement of decision-makers (November)

Activities planned for 2027:

Q1	CoP	Webinar on long-term impact of CCA solutions (February)
	CoP	Online exchange topic TBC (March)
Q2	CoP	Online webinar topic TBC (April)
	CoP	Online exchange topic TBC (May)
Q3	CoP	Workshop TBC (September)
Q4	Col	RESIST session during the European Week of Regions and Cities (October)
	CoP	Online exchange topic TBC (October)
	Col	Open event showcasing project outcomes (December)
	CoP	Final workshop (December)

Table 3 Indicative list of activities 2025-2027

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8 Conclusions

In conclusion, this document outlines the framework for the RESIST Community of Practice, emphasising the critical elements necessary for its establishment, effective management, and ongoing improvement.

The different chapters explore the essential aspects such as the identification of the general purpose of the CoP, the strategies to engage with the target groups, the structure of activities and the definition of roles and responsibilities. The document also describes the activities and strategies carried out and planned to define the RESIST CoP topics and goals and the activities included in the mutual learning and peer-learning schemes.

The planned activities and next steps underscore the dynamic and evolving nature of the RESIST CoP, with a commitment to continuous learning, collaboration, and adaptation. This comprehensive guide for RESIST partners aims to foster a vibrant and impactful Community of Practice in the field of climate change adaptation, with a view to opening learning opportunities to the wider Community of Interest.

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